

PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORT IN THE LIFE OF MODERN SOCIETY

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Annotation: In this article we will describe the role of physical education and sports in the life of modern society and its importance in the life of society. Nowadays, time is developing rapidly, and the development of sports in this place is natural.

KEYWORDS: training, physical training, training, action, competence, skill. Today, sport is an integral part of society's life. Permeating all stages of modern society, it has a great influence on the main spheres of society. Sport affects relations at the national level, the position of a person in society, thereby forming fashion, ethical values, and the way of life of people. In addition to the prevention of bad habits, physical culture satisfies the spectacular demands of humanity. In the XXI century, there is not a single person who would not be engaged in physical culture and sports, did not participate in any competitions, relay races, flash mobs.

The proof of all the above points is that interest in the largest international competitions, such as the Olympic Games, World and European Championships, World University Games is steadily growing. Every second inhabitant of the planet watches these competitions, because these are the most exciting and unpredictable spectacles. Watching the outstanding athletes of the world, people get a storm of emotions that are incomparable. Such major events attract people to physical education and sports. [3.17]

The Uzbek people are ancient and rich, reflecting the good for centuries from the great peoples who have made a great contribution to world civilization with their national culture is one. Sport is very important for presenting our independent Republic to the world. Currently, national games, wrestling and acrobatics are also international. sports - tennis, boxing, football among the Uzbek peoples, we are witnesses that this serves to enhance its reputation. [6.104] Honoring the values, the formation of ancient traditions, the strengthening of beliefs, the transmission of our past cultural heritage from generation to generation to the future generation and in the minds of young people, it is necessary to deeply absorb the essence of national folk games. This

is the issue of Popularization of physical culture and sports in our country, soc. it is defined as one of the important policy directions.

Various diseases, young people prevents bad habits. Sport is a high culture, patriotism also plays an important role in the formation of feelings. Achievements in this field represent the country to the world, make all compatriots proud. Preparation of athletes at the initial stage of training – this skill is one of the most important components of the organization of sports training comprehensive development of the body, health promotion, physical capabilities of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev improvement of the management system in the field of physical culture and sports in October, the development of mass sports, selection and training of talented athletes, industry strengthening by qualified personnel and the construction of modern sports facilities.

Improving the video selector's lecture on development issues and creating a solid functional base for the next stage of preparation is understood as a directed process. What is a person's sports activity purpose and content, or in whatever direction it is carried out, its end is the productivity and efficiency of movement, in turn, the corresponding physical qualities, motor skills, abilities and, of course, the functional capabilities of the body rely on. The female body differs from the male morphologically and functionally, it differs in its anatomical and physiological features. Including puberty in women, the age is up to 34 years, the average age is 35-54 years, the elderly age is up to 55-74 years was calculated. Such age characteristics are primarily biological. The task is also related to maternal functions [2.41]. Daily volume and intensity of activity human health is important in its physical and functional formation, but all types of movement, including sports, are performed in clubs the volume and intensity of physical and technical exercises of the participant must match or exceed its functional capabilities.

Because the biology of ontogenetic development according to the laws proven in science since ancient times is partially influenced by daily physical exertion performed at certain stages. Such negative "traces" trace the normal functional activity of a person, especially young girls relaxes, lowers mood, disrupts sleep and, finally, weakens the ability to work and prevents its full recovery. If such loads are women, if its activity is chronically reduced, it affects the normal growth of the body, not only local or global pathological complications on various functional "objects" are probably the cause of its occurrence.

References:

1. Goncharova O.V. "Physical capabilities of young athletes development". Vol.: 2016. Uzdzhti
2. Bube H., Stubler H., Trogsh F. Tests in sports practice - M.: Physical culture and sport, 1963.
3. Abdurakhmanov M., Makhmudov A. Physical education and sport. Sports medicine. Vol.: 2016. Publishing house "Scientific and technical information-press"

